

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRI. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- When possible, round off numbers to one or two decimal points. For example, 5.2 t/ha, not 5.232.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.
- Type all contributions double-spaced.

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Inheritance of gamma ray-induced multipistillate mutant in rice

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F₁ seed from the cross NSJ 200/Badshah Pasand at 12% moisture content were irradiated with 25 Kr gamma rays from a 60 Co source. In M₂, four 100% male-sterile and multipistillate plants were observed. Each floret consisted of gynoecium with four ovaries and eight styles. All ovaries were fused together, leaving four conspicuous grooves. However, the number of stamens—six—was normal. Both lemma and palea were narrow and semilunar in shape and could not completely cover the androecium and gynoecium. These multipistillate plants produced a few seed that germinated by outcrossing, but the seedlings were poor. A single seed was produced by each floret, indicating that only one pistil was fertile.

In M₃, 30 plant progeny, each consisting of 50 plants, were grown. Six plant progeny segregated into normal and male-sterile multipistillate plants (see table). Of the 300 plants, 16 were male-sterile and multipistillate. Statistical analysis showed that this character is probably governed by duplicate genes ($X^2 = 0.4301$, $P > 0.50$ for 15: 1 ratio). The mutation can be explained

Segregation of six rice plant progeny into male sterile multipistillate plants.^a

Line	Mutants	Normal plants	Total
2	1	49	50
7	3	41	50
9	1	49	50
11	2	48	50
24	5	45	50
28	4	46	50
Total	16	284	300

^a X^2 (15:1) = 0.4301, $P > 0.50$

genetically as follows: Let G₁ and G₂ be duplicate genes, any of which produces normal pistils. When both are homozygous recessive, they produce male-sterile multipistillate plants. The genotype of parents in this case might be G₁G₁G₂G₂ and g₁g₁G₂G₂. The mutation took place at the G₂ locus, involving one of the two alleles.

Diffusion of genetic materials among Asian rice breeding programs

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

Although researchers have studied the spread of the improved rice varieties onto farmers' fields, little is known about their diffusion as parent varieties into breeding programs. Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews with the breeders who made the crosses, IRRI attempted to trace the diffusion of genetic materials used as parents over a 10-year period, from the mid-1960's through the mid-1970's, at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations. The breeders represented 7 centers in India, 2 in Korea, and 1 center each in Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. The research project was partially funded by The Rockefeller Foundation.

Three hundred and fifty-five crosses, involving 819 parents, were randomly selected from the breeding records for 3 time periods: 1965–67, 1970–71 and 1974–75. The percentages of semidwarf, intermediate-statured, tall, and deep-water or floating rices used during each period were calculated on a cross basis—the percentage of total crosses in which a variety of each plant type was used as a donor parent—and on an individual-parent basis—the percentage of different types of rice in the total gene pool.

Sixty-one percent of the 1965–67

Percentages of rices of different plant height used as parents in crosses over a 10-year period. Eight hundred and nineteen parents used in 355 randomly selected crosses at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations, 1965 through 1975.

Plant ht	Rices used (%)		
	1965–67 ^a	1970–71 ^b	1974–75 ^c
	<i>In crosses</i>		
Tall	74	57	45
Intermediate	51	39	35
Semidwarf	61	86	84
Floating/ deep water	2	1	2
	<i>As individual parents</i>		
Tall	40	30	24
Intermediate	31	22	17
Semidwarf	28	48	58
Floating/ deep water	1	–	1

^a277 rice varieties and lines used in 119 crosses.

^b351 rices used in 147 crosses.

^c191 rices used in 89 crosses.

crosses involved at least one semidwarf; and by 1974–75, semidwarf involvement had leveled off at 84% (see table).

Crosses that involved a tall variety dropped from 74% in 1965–67 to 45% in 1974–75.

The intensity of use of semidwarfs as parents increased more than the percentage of crosses involving a semidwarf. In 1965–67, 28% of the total gene pool was semidwarf, and 40% was tall. Ten years later, the percentage of semidwarf material had almost doubled and that of tall and intermediate-statured materials had dropped sharply. That indicates that breeders were increasingly crossing semidwarf parents with other semidwarfs. *W*

Adequacy and importance of resources among rice breeding programs in Asia

Thomas R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

A plant breeder is essentially a “genetic architect.” The tools that he uses to build new rice varieties include such resources as experimental land, greenhouses, scientific information, and

varieties with specific genetic traits to use as parents.

To determine how rice scientists perceive the limitations of such resources, IRRI surveyed 38 rice breeders at 24 research centers in 10 countries as part of a study, initiated in late 1975, of rice breeding in Asia. The project was partially funded by a research grant from The Rockefeller Foundation.

Each breeder was asked to rate the adequacy of each of 14 resource factors – considered important to rice breeding – on a scale of from one to five (1 = very adequate, 5 = very

inadequate). The resources were drawn up by plant scientists from IRRI and from national programs.

The scientists rated “personal freedom to incorporate new breeding materials, techniques, and ideas into the rice improvement program” as the most adequate, with a mean rating of 1.63 (about midway between “adequate” and “very adequate”) (see table). “Availability of genetic materials” received the second highest rating (2.03 or “adequate”). “Availability of experimental land” and “availability and quality of field labor” were also rated as

Ratings of adequacy and importance of resources that influence the work of rice breeders. Thirty-eight rice breeders at 24 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 10 Asian nations, 1975.

Resources	Mean rating of adequacy ^a	Importance score	
		Total ^b	Index ^c
Opportunities for specialized training or advanced education for people who work under you	3.08	49	0.32
Availability of genetic materials with specific genetic characteristics	2.03	46	0.30
Personal freedom to incorporate new breeding materials, techniques, and ideas into the rice improvement program	1.63	45	0.30
Opportunity to have breeding lines thoroughly tested under diverse pest and environmental conditions	2.91	38	0.25
Financial support	3.00	37	0.24
Scientific information resources, such as journals, books, and contact with other scientists, to use in your breeding program	2.83	32	0.21
Availability and quality of trained technical help	2.75	32	0.21
Opportunities for specialized training or advanced education	3.27	17	0.11
Opportunity to gain scientific recognition	3.13	15	0.10
Equipment and tools to use in experiments and breeding work	3.08	12	0.08
Opportunities for professional advancement	3.07	11	0.07
Experimental land	2.11	7	0.05
Transportation	3.25	5	0.03
Availability and quality of labor	2.26	2	0.01
Others (specify)	3.43	10	0.07
Av.	2.99		

^aOn a scale of from 1 to 5: 1 = very adequate at this station; 2 = adequate; 3 = intermediate; 4 = inadequate; 5 = very inadequate.

^bCalculated by assigning a weight of 4 to each factor rated as first in importance by each breeder; 3 to each factor rated second; 2 to each rated third; and 1 to each factor rated fourth. Totals for each factor were then summed. Maximum possible weight per factor was 152 (if all 38 respondents had rated one factor as first in importance).

^cCalculated by dividing total importance score by maximum possible score per factor (152). 1 = most important; 0 = least important.